

Vuzix M4000 Installing and using Teams app

WATERLINE

The logo for Waterline, featuring the word "WATERLINE" in a white, sans-serif font. The letter "A" is replaced by a stylized white water droplet. Below the text is a white, wavy line that resembles a water surface.

Register your Vuzix M4000

Step 1

Visit www.vuzix.com/appstore/user/add-device and log in to your Vuzix account.

Step 2

Follow the instructions to register the device, which will allow you to download apps from the Vuzix App Store.

Installing Microsoft Teams

Step 1

After registering and connecting to Wi-Fi, access the Vuzix App Store on your computer using this link <https://apps.vuzix.com/>

Step 2

At the top of the page, you will see this banner:

All Apps

Click on learn more and fill in the details

A registration form on a dark background. It contains the following fields: "Name" with sub-fields for "First Name" and "Last Name"; "Email"; "Country" with a dropdown menu showing "Select Your Country"; and "Serial Number". At the bottom, there is a checkbox that is checked, with the text "I consent to having Vuzix Corporation collect my details via this form.".

After filling the information, you will then receive an invite by email.

Step 3

Following the link and installing the application. You can now wear your Vuzix M4000 and find Microsoft Teams application.

Using and Joining a Meeting on Teams

Step 1

To schedule a meeting, you can use a PC to set up a formal meeting through the calendar feature in Microsoft Teams. Alternatively, you can initiate an instant video call with a specific user directly within the Teams application. Simply open the app, navigate to the Contacts or Chat section, select the desired contact, and click on the Video Camera icon at the top of the screen to start the call.

Step 2

To join a scheduled meeting, navigate to the **Calendar** tab in Microsoft Teams, locate the meeting you wish to join, and click the **Join** button to enter the session.

Step 3

The Vuzix M4000 user will view the meeting interface through the smart glasses, including participant details, controls for muting, video toggling, and screen sharing.

Meanwhile, the other participants will see a live video stream from the Vuzix M4000, offering a first-person perspective. This perspective allows them to experience what the Vuzix user sees, as displayed in the lower-right corner of their screen.

Step 4

The end user can share their screen, allowing Vuzix M4000 users to view the shared content seamlessly while continuing their work, as illustrated at the bottom.

Note

Meeting recording must be initiated from the desktop version of Teams, as the Vuzix M4000 does not currently support direct recording within the application.